

The Overraching Influence of Aceh Governor Regulations on Superior Legislative Frameworks in the Context of Special Autonomy in Aceh, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The hierarchy of legislation in Indonesia is regulated under Law No. 12 of 2011 (as amended by Law No. 13 of 2022) on the Formation of Laws and Regulations. In the context of Aceh's special autonomy, the Governor holds special authority, but must still adhere to the principle of *lex superior derogat legi inferiori* (a higher law overrides a lower one). The Governor holds special authority but must still comply with the principle of *lex superior derogat legi inferiori* (a higher law overrides a lower one). The main legal basis for Aceh's special autonomy is Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Governance of Aceh. Article 1 point 8 and several other articles grant the Governor the authority to issue Governor Regulations for the implementation of Qanun (Aceh's special regional regulations). This study aims to analyze the dominant influence of Aceh Governor Regulations on superior legislative frameworks in the context of special autonomy in Aceh, Indonesia. The method used in this study is normative legal research. The research findings explain that special autonomy in the province of Aceh is the implementation of Article 18A paragraph (1) and Article 18B paragraph (1) of the Constitution. Indonesia, as a unitary state, places the highest responsibility of governance in the hands of the President. The implementation of governmental affairs may be carried out as broadly as possible as long as it is not limited by law and does not contradict higher-level regulations. The design of asymmetric decentralization in Aceh constitutes a transfer of governmental authority from the President to the region, enabling it to manage and regulate its own governmental affairs. Although the Governor of Aceh holds special authority, Governor Regulations must not contradict Qanun, Government Regulations, or Laws. If such a contradiction occurs, the Governor Regulation may be subject to judicial review and annulled by the Supreme Court.

Keywords: Governor Regulation, Special Autonomy, Asymmetric Decentralization

[Introduction](#)
[Literature Review](#)
[Discussion](#)
[Conclusion](#)
[References](#)

1. INTRODUCTION

Article 18B paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia states that "the state recognizes and respects regional government units that are special or have special characteristics, as regulated by law." This provision serves as the constitutional basis for granting special autonomy to certain regions, including Aceh. Special autonomy for Aceh is provided through Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Governance of Aceh, which aims to accommodate Aceh specific needs and characteristics, such as the implementation of Islamic law (Sharia), the management of natural resources, and the recognition of local customs and culture. Within the framework of special autonomy, the Aceh Government, based on the provisions of Law No. 23 of 2014 on Regional Government, acknowledges that all provinces in Indonesia are granted broad authority, except in matters of absolute government authority that fall under the central government (such as defense, foreign affairs, national fiscal and monetary policy, and others). However, Aceh can claim broader authority than other provinces because it possesses a stronger and specific legal foundation, namely:

1. **Constitutional Basis (Article 18B of the 1945 Constitution).**
2. **Special Law: Law No. 11 of 2006 on the Government of Aceh** Several special provisions that form the basis for Aceh's claim to broader authority include:
 - **Local legislative authority:** Aceh has Qanun (Islamic by-laws) as regional regulations that functionally hold a higher status within its jurisdiction, even regulating matters not covered by Law No. 23 of 2014.
 - **Legal system:** Aceh is permitted to implement laws based on Islamic Sharia, including the operation of Mahkamah Syar'iyah (Sharia Courts), which are equivalent to Religious Courts.
 - **Local politics:** Aceh is the only region allowed to have local political parties.
 - **Natural resource management:** Aceh has a greater share in the management and revenue of natural resources, such as oil and gas.
3. The legal principle of *Lex Specialis Derogat Legi Generali* means that: The Law on the Government of Aceh, as a *lex specialis*, overrides Law No. 23 of 2014 in the event of a conflict. This means that the provisions in the Law on the Government of Aceh are binding and take precedence over the general provisions in the Regional Government Law.

According to article 7 paragraph (1) of the law on Aceh Governance, "The Aceh Government has the authority to regulate and administer governmental affairs in all sectors, except for governmental affairs that fall under the authority of the central government." However, in the implementation of this authority, challenges often arise in formulating regulations that align with national interests, applicable laws, and the local needs of the Acehnese people (Ainun Najah, Faza: 2025). As a region with asymmetric decentralization, Aceh is frequently confronted with a dilemma between fulfilling local needs and aspirations while maintaining consistency with the principles of the rule of law and the hierarchy of legal regulations (Ainun Najah, Faza: 2025). **Through Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Governance of Aceh**, the region was granted special autonomy, including in matters of **religious life (particularly Islamic Sharia)**. For example, **Aceh Governor Regulation No.**

5 of 2015 regulates the recruitment requirements for regional contract workers. It was deemed discriminatory because it **required all applicants to be able to read the Qur'an**, regardless of job field exceeding national standards. Other **Aceh Governor Regulations related to Islamic Sharia** (such as **the prohibition for non-Muslims to open food stalls during the daytime in Ramadan**) also sparked **debate**, as they were seen as infringing on the **constitutional rights of citizens** and the **principle of pluralism** guaranteed by the **1945 Constitution**. Furthermore, the **Qanun Jinayat** (Islamic criminal law) and the **Qanun Acara Jinayat** (its procedural code) have drawn **criticism** because, despite being legitimate under special autonomy, their **implementation often overlaps with the national Criminal Code (KUHP)**. Some Aceh Governor Regulations have been deemed to exceed the scope of authority granted by national legislation, leading to debates over their legal validity.

Based on Article 246 paragraph (1) of Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government states that the Governor issues a Governor Regulation to implement a Regional Regulation or based on the authority granted by higher legislation." Article 18 paragraphs (2) and (5) of the 1945 Constitution provide the constitutional basis for regional autonomy, namely the authority to regulate and manage their own governmental affairs." Furthermore, Article 242 of Law No. 11 of 2006 concerning the Governance of Aceh grants the Governor the authority to issue Governor Regulations for the implementation of Qanun." Qanun Number 11 of 2002 serves as the legal basis for the implementation of Islamic Sharia in Aceh and remains relevant after the Helsinki MoU, despite being enacted before the Aceh Governance Law." The Governor of Aceh Regulation, such as Governor Regulation Number 49 of 2006, is a concrete implementation of the authority of regional autonomy as stipulated in the Law on the Governance of Aceh. This regulation affirms the technical implementation of Sharia Law in accordance with the Qanun and highlights the role of Governor Regulations as instruments that accommodate regional interests while ensuring alignment with the national legal framework. In addition, Aceh Government Regulation Number 3 of 2017 concerning Procedures for the Discussion and Approval of the Aceh Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget.

In relation to the authority to issue Governor Regulations, there are several Governor Regulations that have been issued by the Governor of Aceh which contain provisions that are not in accordance with or contradict higher-level legislation. One such regulation is Aceh Governor Regulation Number 49 of 2016 concerning the Provision of Exclusive Breastfeeding. This regulation was enacted on August 11, 2016, and remains in effect to this day. Among other things, the regulation provides for six months of leave within the civil service for childbirth and breastfeeding. Additionally, it allows male employees to take seven days of leave to accompany their wives during childbirth and to assist in caring for their newborn children.

However, regarding the authority to issue Governor Regulations, several Aceh Governor Regulations contain provisions that contradict higher-level legislation. One such regulation is Aceh Governor Regulation Number 49 of 2016 concerning the Provision of Exclusive Breastfeeding, which grants six months of leave for civil servants for childbirth and breastfeeding, as well as seven days of leave for male employees to accompany their wives during childbirth. However, Government Regulation Number 11 of 2017 and

Government Regulation Number 24 of 1976 stipulate that maternity leave is only three months, so the leave duration in this Governor Regulation contradicts the applicable government regulations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In addition to the Governor of Aceh issued Aceh Governor Regulation Number 53 of 2020 concerning Procedures for Granting Grants to Dayah funded by the Aceh Revenue and Expenditure Budget, where Article 7 paragraph (2) states that grant disbursement may be carried out continuously every year according to Aceh financial capacity." This provision differs from the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 77 of 2020 on Regional Financial Management, which states that grant expenditures are non-mandatory, non-binding, and not provided continuously every fiscal year to various parties with specifically designated purposes" These two regulations actually address different contexts: **Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 77 of 2020** is a national regulation that provides general guidelines for the implementation of duties and coordination of regional governance, applicable to all regions in Indonesia, including Aceh. In contrast, **Aceh Governor Regulation Number 53 of 2020** is a regional regulation that accommodates Aceh special provisions as a region with special autonomy, tailored to local needs, culture, and the specific autonomy regulations applicable in Aceh. This Governor Regulation accommodates: (1) The adjustment of governance tasks in accordance with Aceh's characteristics as a special autonomous region; (2) Coordination mechanisms and the implementation of governmental affairs that take into account local wisdom, customs, and existing qanun regulations in Aceh; (3) Arrangements for the implementation of governance policies in line with the mandate of the Law on the Governance of Aceh and other related regulations; and (4) The provision of flexibility for the Aceh government to manage governmental affairs according to the needs and conditions that differ from other regions in Indonesia.

In addition to the Governor Regulation mentioned above, there is also Aceh Governor Regulation Number 46 of 2009 concerning the Use of the Name Aceh and Titles of Government Officials in Official Correspondence within the Aceh Government. This Governor Regulation governs the name "Aceh" as the name of the province. However, this is not in accordance with the provisions of Article 251 paragraph (3) of the Law on the Governance of Aceh, which states that "the name Aceh as a provincial region in the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia system, based on the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, and the titles of elected government officials will be determined by the Aceh People's Representative Council after the 2009 general election, as established by Government Regulation based on proposals from the Aceh People's Representative Council and the Governor of Aceh (Wijayanti & Putri, Anindyajati: 2021)." The normative conflict lies in the difference in authority and the procedure for forming legal norms, namely: Governor Regulation 46/2009 independently establishes provisions that, by law, must be regulated through a Government Regulation based on a joint mechanism between the Aceh People's Representative Council, and the Governor. Therefore, this Governor Regulation

contradicts higher-level legislation (the Law on the Governance of Aceh) and can be considered legally flawed both procedurally and substantively.

Some of the Governor Regulations described above, although not in accordance with the provisions of higher laws and regulations, either in terms of content that contradicts or in terms of the type of legal product that does not comply with the mandate of higher regulations, have nevertheless been implemented as the legal basis for the policies of the Aceh Government and are accepted/recognized by the Central Government. Law Number 11 of 2006 on the Governance of Aceh (Aceh Government Law) is recognized as a *lex specialis* that takes precedence over higher-level regulations. The implementation of Aceh Governor Regulations that conflict with national legal products continues due to the legitimacy provided by the Aceh Government Law, accommodation from the central government (*de facto* acceptance), and support through circular letters or administrative practices, until the legal conflict is resolved through judicial institutions. Anindyajati, Wijayanti & Putri, in the *Jurnal Konstitusi*, provide a legal analysis of the implementation of the principle of *lex specialis derogat legi generali* in Aceh. They explain that the Law on the Governance of Aceh, as a special law, holds the authority to deviate from or override general norms in the vertical relationship between the central government and Aceh. **The implementation of Islamic law is part of the special autonomy of Aceh as a region with specific privileges and distinctions, among which is "related to one of the distinctive characteristics of the historical struggle of the Acehnese people, who have high resilience and fighting spirit, derived from a worldview based on Islamic law that has given birth to a strong Islamic culture."**

Another region in Indonesia that also has special characteristics is Papua. In Law Number 21 of 2001 concerning Special Autonomy for the Province of Papua, there is a type of legal product specifically regulated for the implementation of its special autonomy, namely the "Special Regional Regulation, which is a Regional Regulation of Papua Province enacted to implement certain articles in this Law (the Special Autonomy Law). Besides the Special Regional Regulation, the Law also regulates the "Provincial Regional Regulation, which is the Provincial Regulation of Papua Province in the context of implementing the authorities as stipulated in the legislation.

This means that Papua has regional regulations which, from the name of the product itself, can already be identified as legal products implementing both asymmetric decentralization and symmetric decentralization. However, in Aceh, based on the Law on Aceh Government, Article 1 point 21 states that Qanun Aceh are legislative regulations similar to provincial regulations that govern the administration of government and community life in Aceh. It can be concluded that in Aceh, legislative regulations similar to regional regulations are called Qanun. Qanun are not only for implementing asymmetric decentralization but also for implementing symmetric decentralization, as in other regions. Therefore, to determine whether a Qanun is a Special Qanun (implementing asymmetric decentralization) or a General Qanun (implementing symmetric decentralization), it cannot be known without analyzing its content.

Aceh is a special or distinctive regional government unit, characterized by its unique historical struggle of the Acehnese people, who possess strong resilience and fighting spirit

rooted in a worldview based on Islamic Sharia, which has given rise to a strong Islamic culture. In the implementation of its special autonomy policy, regulations are needed to provide legal legitimacy for its execution. In 2014, with the enactment of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, the principles for administering regional governance, given the vast territory of Indonesia, received a constitutional foundation through the 1945 Constitution and its amendments, which provide the legal basis for regional governance in Indonesia. Among the provisions are:

- a. The principle of recognition and respect by the state for the unity of customary law communities and their traditional rights, as long as they still exist and are in line with societal development and the principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.
- b. The principle that regions regulate and manage their own governmental affairs based on the principles of autonomy and co-administration.
- c. The principle of exercising the broadest possible autonomy.
- d. The principle of recognizing and respecting regional governments with special and unique status.
- e. The principle that representative bodies are directly elected in general elections.
- f. The principle that relations between central and regional governments must be carried out harmoniously and fairly.
- g. The principle that the distribution of authority between the central and regional governments must take into account the uniqueness and diversity of regions.
- h. The principle that financial relations, public services, and the use of natural and other resources between the central and regional governments must be carried out fairly and harmoniously in accordance with the law.
- i. The principle of state recognition and respect for regional government units with special or distinctive characteristics.

Another issue addressed is that regional regulations issued by regencies/municipalities may be annulled by the Governor or Deputy Governor. However, the regency/municipality has the right to submit an appeal to the Ministry of Home Affairs. If the Ministry upholds the Governor's decision, the regency/municipality may then file for a judicial review with the Supreme Court (Taufik Rachman: 2014). When compared to Law Number 32 of 2004, Law Number 23 of 2014 is significantly better, as it envisions Indonesia moving more clearly toward decentralization.

According to Nurfurqon emphasizes that asymmetric decentralization provides legitimate space for special regions to formulate their own norms, as long as they do not conflict with fundamental constitutional norms, normative conflicts can be justified in a limited and constitutional manner within the framework of asymmetric decentralization (Ardika Nurfurqon: 2020), provided that: The authority to establish regional norms is legitimate, meaning it is granted by law (for example, the Law on the Governance of Aceh or the Special Autonomy Law for Papua). The conflicting norms do not violate fundamental constitutional principles, such as state sovereignty, human rights, or the system of government. Why is it justified? Because asymmetric decentralization is specifically designed to accommodate the uniqueness of certain regions, whether in terms of culture, religion, history, or politics. In this context, certain regions are allowed to create regulations

that differ (and sometimes even substantively conflict) with national norms, as long as they remain within the framework of national law. For example: Aceh is permitted to implement Sharia law in its social life through the issuance of Qanuns, and even though these norms differ from the national legal system in general (Aryos Nivada: 2028).

Gunawan A. Tauda (2018) stated in his paper to ensure that asymmetric decentralization remains within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, it must meet the following principles: (1) Originates from Constitutional Mandate and Legislation; the uniqueness of a region must be based on national law, not the result of unilateral separation of power by the region, (2) Remains Recognized and Supervised by the Central Government; Although granted broad autonomy, regional regulations (including Qanuns or Governor Regulations) remain subject to evaluation, supervision, and annulment by the central government if they conflict with higher-level laws and regulations, (3) Does Not Touch on Matters of State Symbolism; For example: defense, foreign policy, and monetary matters remain under the control of the central government, and (4) Local Norms Must Be Consistent with the Principles of Human Rights and Diversity Differences in norms must not cause discrimination that violates human rights or threatens national unity.

Based on the description above, it provides a clear picture of the ideal formulation of legal norms and legislation that support the implementation of special autonomy. This becomes the main motivation for the author in producing findings, studies, and analyses about **"The Overarching Influence of Aceh Governor Regulations on Superior Legislative Frameworks in the Context of Special Autonomy in Aceh, Indonesia."**

Some of the series of questions from this research study are:

1. Main Research Question: To what extent do Aceh Governor Regulations have influence or implications on higher legal norms in the context of special autonomy in Aceh ?
2. Sub-Research Questions
 - A. In relation to authority and legality
 - ♦ What is the legal basis for the issuance of Aceh Governor Regulations within the special autonomy system ?
 - ♦ Is the authority of the Governor of Aceh to issue regulations in accordance with the Law on the Governance of Aceh (UUPA) and the 1945 Constitution ?
 - ♦ In the context of constitutional law, can a Governor Regulation have normative implications for higher-level regulations ?
 - B. Concerning Norm Conflicts
 - ♦ What are some examples of Aceh Governor Regulations that conflict with national legislation ?
 - ♦ How is the mechanism for resolving normative conflicts between Aceh Governor Regulations and national regulations ?
 - C. Related to the Context of Special Autonomy
 - ♦ How does the design of asymmetric decentralization in Aceh allow regulatory flexibility through Governor Regulations ?
 - ♦ Does Aceh's special status under the Law on the Governance of Aceh justify Governor Regulations that are substantively in conflict with national regulations?

The novelty of this research lies in: (1) the analysis of the **bottom-up influence** of Governor Regulations on national law, which remains underexplored; (2) a **specific study of the normative mechanism** of Aceh Governor Regulations within the **vertical legal relationship** (Aceh vs. the national government), particularly in the post-reform and contemporary context; and (3) the emphasis on the **conflict between the principle of lex specialis derogat legi generali** (the Law on the Governance of Aceh as special law) and the **principle of lex superior derogat legi inferiori** (higher law overrides lower law). Meanwhile, the urgency of this study stems from the **ongoing legal conflicts between Aceh and the central government**, which require deeper academic and legal analysis as well as practical resolution.

3. DISCUSSION

1. The theory of governor regulations compared to higher-level regulations can be justified on the basis of asymmetric decentralization

Historically, regional autonomy in Indonesia began to be implemented with the enactment of Law Number 1 of 1945, followed by the issuance of Law Number 2 of 1984 and Law Number 5 of 1974 concerning the Principles of Regional Government. These two regulations aimed to ensure equitable development across all regions could be optimally achieved. However, during its initial implementation, many obstacles and challenges arose, which were later resolved more comprehensively during the reform era. After the end of the 'New Order' era, laws regarding the delegation of authority between regional and central governments could finally be implemented as stipulated in **Law Number 22 of 1999**. Over time, and with the strict supervision of the central government, the implementation of **decentralization** the delegation of power from the central government to regional governments was successfully carried out, in line with the expectations of each region. The essence of regional government is to carry out optimal government and administrative functions and systems, while the Regional House of Representatives functions to perform legislative, budgeting, and oversight duties. Therefore, as part of the regional government system, the Regional House of Representatives should participate in the improvement of policies established in the region, especially Regional Regulations (Boemiya: 2020).

Furthermore, Gunawan A. Tauda explains in "**The Design of Asymmetric Decentralization in the Constitutional System of the Republic of Indonesia**" that the 1945 Constitution [Articles 18A(1) & 18B(1)] provides juridical recognition of asymmetric decentralization. This allows certain regions, such as Aceh, to implement designs of authority, institutions, finances, and control that differ from the general national pattern." Kadek Cahya Susila Wibawa (2019) emphasizes that the relationship between the central and regional governments in Indonesia exists on a continuum between unitarism and federalism. The state needs to establish a policy foundation for asymmetric decentralization so that regional autonomy can be implemented in accordance with the legal-political framework of the 1945 Constitution. Meanwhile, Bayu Satria Utama (2019) highlights how asymmetric decentralization has been used as a political strategy to mitigate post-reform

conflict in Aceh local legitimacy through specific regulations is granted operational space as long as it has not been legally annulled.

The Law on the Governing of Aceh (UUPA, Law No. 11/2006) serves as a form of lex specialis for Aceh, which, according to the principle lex specialis derogat legi generali, may override or deviate from general national laws in the event of a conflict. The framework of vertical legal relations, this provides a formal basis for Aceh regulations (such as Governor Regulations and Qanun) to operate uniquely and potentially not align with national legislation. In the context of a vertical legal relationship, this provides a formal basis for Aceh regulations to operate in a distinctive manner, which may not necessarily align with national laws.

In many cases, the Aceh House of Representatives has exercised its right of interpellation against gubernatorial policies deemed problematic. For example, the right of interpellation was exercised at least nine times during the Irwandi–Nova administration, targeting policies considered poor in governance or in conflict with the law. The Aceh House of Representatives is also active in evaluating draft qanuns; one example is its handling of political conflict related to the Wali Nanggroe Qanun, where the DPRA avoided enacting a qanun that could provoke controversy and potential conflict.

From the sociological implications, this results in normative resistance and active criticism when policies are perceived as not reflecting public needs and local wisdom. Public participation is considered vital to maintaining good governance, meaning the involvement of the community to prevent domination by political power. So, from a juridical implication, the use of the right of interpellation and lawsuits demonstrates the existence of legal-institutional methods to examine, annul, or revise local policies; and the Minister of Home Affairs regulation or the Supreme Court can annul regional regulations if they are proven to conflict with higher regulations or are substantively invalid. **From Political Implications**, the increasing competition between the local executive and legislative bodies can hinder governance if not balanced with effective communication; and concerns about creeping recentralization arise when regulatory conflicts recur, prompting demands for central government intervention.

2. The three foundations of the Governor of Aceh's regulations The three legal foundations that support the normative analysis of the Governor of Aceh's Regulations are:

- 2.1. Constitutional Basis: Article 18B of the 1945 Constitution

Article 18B paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution states: “The state recognizes and respects regional government units that are special or distinctive, as regulated by law.” This statement directly provides a constitutional basis for the existence of special autonomy (such as in Aceh and Papua). In other words, the practice of specific regulations in Aceh, including Governor Regulations that deviate from national standards, has a strong constitutional foundation.

Article 18B paragraph (1) indicates that special autonomy is not merely an administrative policy, but possesses inherent constitutional authority. Article 18B paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution is not merely a symbolic recognition, but serves as the highest legal foundation for regions with special status to govern and formulate regulations in accordance with their specific characteristics. In the context of Aceh, regulations such as Governor Regulations that are specific or differ from national standards remain valid and constitutional, as they are derived from the special autonomy rights guaranteed by the Constitution.

2.2. Special Law: Aceh Government Law (Law No. 11/2006)

The Aceh Government Law is a special legislative product based on Article 18B and established through the Helsinki MoU. Some key points of the UUPA: Article 269 paragraph (2) affirms that "Regulations under the law directly related to special autonomy... shall be adjusted in accordance with this Law." The explanation of Law Number 11 of 2006 emphasizes that Qanun and Governor Regulations (Pergub) are very important and concrete legal instruments in the implementation of Aceh's special autonomy authority. In other words, these two types of regulations are not merely ordinary rules but serve as the main means for the Aceh government to implement the constitutional rights and powers recognized by the 1945 Constitution and the Aceh Government Law.

Qanun, as a local legislative product enacted by the Aceh House of Representatives (DPRA), functions as regional regulations that have binding legal force within Aceh. These Qanun allow Aceh to regulate various aspects of governance and community life according to local characteristics, culture, and needs, which may differ from national regulations. For example, Qanun may cover customary law, local government systems, natural resource management, and unique socio-cultural aspects of Aceh. Meanwhile, Governor Regulations are implementing regulations issued by the Governor of Aceh to govern technical and operational matters in the administration of local government in accordance with the framework of Qanun and the Aceh Government Law. Governor Regulations enables the local government to regulate policies in a more detailed and flexible manner required for the implementation of special autonomy, as well as to adjust to conditions and dynamics that develop on the ground.

Through Qanun and Pergub, Aceh can exercise broad authority independently, ranging from regional financial management, regulation of customary practices, implementation of Islamic law (Sharia), to regional development policies aligned with the aspirations of the Acehnese people. This is a tangible manifestation of constitutional recognition of Aceh special autonomy, which provides ample space for the region to innovate and manage its internal affairs without being fully dependent on national regulations. Thus, Qanun and Governor Regulations are not only administrative instruments but also embodiments of Aceh sovereignty and independence within the framework of the

Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, in accordance with the guarantees provided by Article 18B of the 1945 Constitution and the Aceh Government Law.

2.3. Legal Principle: *Lex Specialis Derogat Legi Generali*

This principle states that special law (*lex specialis*) overrides general law in cases of conflict. The Law on the Governing of Aceh is a *lex specialis* for Aceh. If it conflicts with Law No. 23 of 2014 on Regional Government, the UUPA holds greater legal authority within the context of Aceh. The Law on the Governing of Aceh itself mandates the revision of regulations that contradict this *lex specialis* (Article 269 paragraph 2). Legally, this allows Aceh's Governor Regulations or Qanuns to deviate from Law No. 23/2014.

The Governor of Aceh continues to issue regulations that, in terms of legal hierarchy, may conflict with higher-level laws, due to the following reason: Aceh has been granted special autonomy status under **Law Number 11 of 2006 on the Governing of Aceh**. This status was given as a form of recognition of Aceh's unique history, culture, and political aspirations, which differ from those of other regions in Indonesia. Special autonomy provides Aceh with broader authority than other regions, including the power to enact regional regulations that are unique and may differ from national policies.

Febriana & Zulkarnain (2025), in their article titled "64 Years of Aceh Special Status: A Review of Law No. 11/2006 on the Governing of Aceh," provide a brief explanation as follows:

- Aceh special status has been inherent since the colonial period and the struggle for independence, particularly marked by the strong practice of Islamic Sharia in the daily life of its people.
- The response to Aceh religious distinctiveness began in 1959 through the MISSI HARDI initiative, and culminated in the formal enactment of Law No. 11 of 2006, which serves as the legal foundation for Aceh special autonomy.
- Law No. 11/2006 covers legal, political, and educational arrangements specific to Aceh, which are implemented based on Islamic Sharia principles and local wisdom. The law also establishes mechanisms for the application of Sharia through Acehnese Qanuns, which include aspects of the judiciary, family law, education, and other religious activities.

MISSI HARDI became the starting point of political recognition of the Acehnese community's aspiration to implement Islamic teachings more substantively in social and state life. This long journey culminated in the enactment of **Law Number 11 of 2006 on the Governing of Aceh (UUPA)** as part of the national reconciliation efforts following the prolonged conflict between the Free Aceh Movement (GAM) and the Government of the Republic of Indonesia. The **Governing of Aceh** is not only a political product resulting from the peace agreement (Helsinki MoU 2005) but also a legal and constitutional symbol of the state's full recognition of Aceh's historical, cultural, and religious identity. The **Governing of Aceh** provides a unique and distinct legal framework for Aceh to exercise its special autonomy. Unlike other regions, Aceh is granted full authority to regulate: (1) Local laws based on Islamic Sharia, such as jinayat qanuns and family qanuns; (2) Local politics, including the establishment of local political parties that are not allowed in other regions; (3) Local education that reflects Islamic values and the local wisdom of the Acehnese people.

Through Aceh qanuns, the implementation of Sharia law acquires formal legal form, covering judicial aspects (with the establishment of the Sharia Court), family law (marriage, inheritance, divorce), Islamic education, and religious and social activities. Thus, the **Governing of Aceh** affirms Aceh position as a region with legal legitimacy to operate a socio-political system based on Islamic values and local customs, as long as it remains within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). This reflects a model of asymmetric decentralization, where not all regions are treated equally but are given different authorities according to their needs and historical background.

3. Governor regulations are still justifiable to maintain, even though there is a normative conflict

Asymmetric decentralization is a form of decentralization in which certain regions are granted broader authority than others, tailored to their specific needs, socio-cultural characteristics, and historical context. In the Indonesian context, clear examples include **Aceh, Papua, and DKI Jakarta. Its main objectives are:** to accommodate the uniqueness of certain regions (such as Islamic law in Aceh or indigenous rights in Papua); to prevent disintegration by recognizing and involving local politics; and to offer flexible solutions to the complexity of diversity within a unitary state.

In principle, asymmetric decentralization can provide legal justification for the existence of regional policies or regulations (including Governor Regulations) that deviate from national rules, as long as they are enacted based on special legal frameworks, such as: **Law No. 11 of 2006 on the Governance of Aceh; Article 18B paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution**, which recognizes regional governments with special or privileged status. For example, **if a regulation issued by the Governor of Aceh contradicts Law No. 23 of 2014** (on Regional Government), then the principle of *lex specialis derogat legi generali* may apply (a specific law overrides a general one). Amrizal J. Prang (2020), in his book *Asymmetric Decentralization in Aceh*, explains that the relationship between Aceh and the central government is not one of subordination, but rather coordination based on attributed authority.

The Law on the Governance of Aceh (UUPA) also established the Sharia Court as part of the national judicial system. For example, **Qanun Aceh** is enforced as a legal instrument for the implementation of Islamic law, covering: **Jinayat justice** (Islamic criminal law); **Islamic family law** (marriage, inheritance, divorce), and **regulations on religious education and Islamic-based social activities.** It is affirmed that the implementation of Islamic law in Aceh does not conflict with the 1945 Constitution, as it is based on the principle of asymmetric decentralization.

Addressing normative conflicts within the framework of asymmetric decentralization is a significant challenge in Indonesia's legal and governance system. Normative conflict arises when there is a contradiction between regional regulations enacted under special authority (*lex specialis*) and national regulations of a general nature (*lex generalis*). In the context of asymmetric decentralization as seen in regions like Aceh, Papua, or DKI Jakarta such conflicts become increasingly complex because these areas possess specific legal foundations that govern their special authorities.

4. Ways to Resolve Norm Conflicts within the Framework of Asymmetric Decentralization

To prevent the recurrence of normative conflicts in Aceh especially in the context of enforcing Islamic principles through Governor Regulations or Qanun a holistic approach is needed. This approach should not rely solely on positive law, but must also take into account aspects of constitutionality, community involvement, central-local government coordination, and legal harmonization. The following is a more detailed explanation:

4.1. The Application of the Principle of *Lex Specialis Derogat Legi Generali*

The principle of *lex specialis derogat legi generali* means that specific laws override general laws. In this context: (1) If a regional regulation in Aceh (such as a qanun) conflicts with the Law on Regional Government (Law No. 23 of 2014), then **Law No. 11 of 2006 on the Governing of Aceh** can be used as the legal basis for overriding it, as it constitutes *lex specialis*; (2) Strengthening the understanding of this principle among policymakers and law enforcement officials is essential, so that substantively legitimate regional regulations are not annulled merely because they do not conform to general national norms.

4.2. Affirmation of Hierarchy and Harmonization of Regulations

- The drafting and evaluation of regulations must be carried out with due regard to the hierarchy of legislation (based on Law No. 12 of 2011 in conjunction with Law No. 13 of 2022).

- For regions with special status, the evaluation of qanun or special regional regulations cannot be equated with ordinary regional regulations. A special mechanism needs to be implemented by the Ministry of Home Affairs or related institutions, involving local actors (for example, the Aceh Regional House of Representatives).

- Harmonization of regulations between the central and regional governments is needed to prevent unnecessary normative conflicts.

4.3. Optimization of the Role of the Supreme Court and the Constitutional Court

Normative conflicts can be resolved judicially through judicial review:

- **Supreme Court:** reviews regional regulations against higher regulations (for example, qanun against laws).

- **Constitutional Court:** reviews laws against the 1945 Constitution, including assessing the conformity of asymmetric decentralization with the principle of the unitary state.

4.4. Dialogue and Consultative Mechanism between Central and Regional Governments

In accordance with Government Regulation Number 12 of 2017 pertaining to the Supervision and Guidance of Regional Government Administration, the Home Affairs Minister conducts general guidance and supervision over matters within the authority of provincial and regency/municipality governments, including facilitating the resolution of regional regulation and regional head regulation issues. Aceh, which is a special region established by Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Government of Aceh (Aceh Government Law), in Article 235 paragraph (1) states that government supervision of qanun is carried out in accordance with the laws and regulations.

Law No. 11 of 2006 and similar regulations require a consultation mechanism between the central government and special regional governments; In the context of Aceh, for example, the formulation of national policies that affect the region must take into account the views of the Governor and the Aceh Regional House of Representatives; and Strengthening this consultative forum serves as a political and administrative solution to

prevent or resolve normative conflicts from the outset. The provision of Article 246 paragraph (1) of the Regional Government Law states that "to implement regional regulations or by the authority of legislation, the Governor establishes Governor Regulations."

4.5. Strengthening the Capacity of Human Resources and Regulatory Authorities

Many normative conflicts occur due to a lack of understanding among policymakers regarding the limits of their authority and the principles of legal drafting; and there is a need for ongoing legal and regulatory training, especially for members of the Regional People's Representative Council, regional legal bureaus, and local government officials.

Resolving normative conflicts within the framework of asymmetric decentralization requires a multi-level approach: legal, political, administrative, and educational. The key principle is recognizing the uniqueness of special regions without compromising the integrity of the national legal system. If the *lex specialis* mechanism is properly applied and center–regional dialogue is optimized, normative conflicts can be minimized, and regional autonomy can be maintained within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Wamafma explains that **asymmetric decentralization or special autonomy** is a form of autonomy granted to a specific region to govern itself (to manage and administer its own affairs), by providing special rights with a higher degree of independence compared to other regions.

Anang Puji Utama (2025) explains that **asymmetric decentralization or special autonomy** can be one of the necessary steps to maintain harmony between the central and regional governments, both among governmental institutions and with communities or social groups. The special autonomy granted to Papua and Aceh is essentially a soft option offered by the central government in response to separatist demands from local populations, which question issues of justice, identity clarity, historical integration, and quality of life.

Thus, the implementation of asymmetric decentralization in Indonesia has a clear constitutional foundation, namely Article 18B paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. This provision stipulates that the state recognizes and respects regional government units that are special or have special status, as regulated by law.

4. CONCLUSION

One of the forms of Aceh special status that is constitutionally recognized is the implementation of Islamic law. This special status is regulated under Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Governance of Aceh, which grants special authority to Aceh to organize community life based on Islamic law (*sharia*). However, the implementation of Islamic law in Aceh operates within the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI), which, constitutionally, is not a religious state but a state based on Pancasila, whose first principle is "Belief in One Supreme God." This means that Indonesia guarantees freedom of religion but does not adopt any one religion as the basis of the state.

In a state governed by the rule of law such as Indonesia, all legal products must adhere to the hierarchy of legislation (the principle of *lex superior derogat legi inferiori*). If a Governor Regulation conflicts with a higher law (for example, the 1945 Constitution or Law

No. 11/2006), it violates the principle of the supremacy of law, which holds that higher laws must serve as the primary reference. Such conflicting regulations may be annulled by the central government through the mechanism for canceling regional legal products by the Ministry of Home Affairs (Article 251 of Law No. 23/2014 on Regional Government).

As a unitary state, Indonesia places the central government as the highest authority within the governmental system. If a region (in this case, Aceh) implements policies that conflict with national law: It may give the impression of excessive discretion by the region, which could be perceived as a form of “administrative separatism.” The potential for horizontal conflict increases, especially if the regulation touches on sensitive aspects such as religion, human rights, or civil liberties in a multicultural area.

The asymmetric decentralization design in Aceh is the transfer of governmental power from the president to the region to manage and administer its own governmental affairs. The implementation of those governmental affairs is carried out to the fullest extent as long as it is not restricted by law.

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